

Cross-Domain Solution for Secure Tamper-Proof Logging

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Abstract

Secure cross-domain information transfer remains a critical challenge in network security, particularly when moving data between networks with different security classifications. This paper presents a novel Cross-Domain Solution (CDS) for secure, tamper-proof logging that leverages a unidirectional fiber optic data diode to enable safe information transfer from a low-security to a high-security network. The proposed solution employs a Labeled Transition System (LTS) model to formally specify and verify the system's security properties. Key innovations include a strict unidirectional information flow, perfect forward secrecy, and robust message integrity mechanisms. The system comprises three computers across two network domains, utilizing a 50/50 fiber optic splitter and media converters to ensure one-way data transmission. The LTS model rigorously defines the system's state space, action set, and transition relations, demonstrating critical security properties such as noninterference, information flow control, and forward secrecy. Specifically, the solution guarantees that: (1) information only flows from low to high security domains, (2) message contents are immediately deleted after confirmation, and (3) stored logs are immutable and tamper-proof. Implemented using APU2 boards and TP-Link media converters, this approach offers a practical, plug-and-play solution for secure cross-domain logging that addresses key challenges in maintaining information security across network boundaries. The formal verification approach provides a comprehensive framework for analyzing and ensuring the system's security properties.

1 Introduction

The secure transfer of information between networks of different security classifications represents a critical challenge in modern cybersecurity architectures. Cross Domain Solutions (CDS) facilitate this transfer while maintaining strict security boundaries between networks classified at different security levels [1]. In particular, the unidirectional transfer of data from lower security domains to higher security domains presents a fundamental scenario with applications in military networks, critical infrastructure, industrial control systems, and secure logging environments [2].

Traditional approaches to solving the cross-domain communication problem include air-gap isolation, where networks are physically separated with manual data transfer processes. While effective for security, air-gap solutions introduce significant operational inefficiencies and create bottlenecks in time-sensitive workflows [3]. To address these limitations, several technologies have emerged to enable secure, automated cross-domain data transfers while preserving security domain separation.

A comprehensive survey on cross-domain solutions lists Bell-Lapadula confidentiality[4], BIBA integrity and assured pipeline security models to be relevant[5]. The U.S. Naval Research Laboratory's Network Pump represents an early technological approach to the cross-domain communication challenge, implementing a statistical flow control mechanism to mitigate covert channel risks [6]. The Network Pump introduces probabilistic delays in acknowledgment packets to minimize the bandwidth of potential covert timing channels

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while maintaining reliable data transfer between domains [7]. This approach prioritizes security guarantees while accepting some performance trade-offs.

Data diodes represent another class of cross-domain solutions, implementing hardware-enforced unidirectional information flow through either optical isolation or other physical means [8]. Commercial data diode implementations typically involve proprietary hardware and software components, resulting in significant acquisition and maintenance costs that may be prohibitive for smaller organizations or research environments [5].

In the specific domain of secure logging, cross-domain architectures face additional requirements beyond basic unidirectional data transfer [9]. These include guarantees of message delivery, message integrity verification, tamper-resistant storage, and perfect forward secrecy [10]. Current solutions often require specialized hardware, complex software stacks, and substantial configuration efforts, limiting their accessibility and deployment [11].

This paper introduces a free, plug-and-play cross-domain solution for securely transferring data from low to high security domains using commercially available off-the-shelf components. Our approach focuses specifically on secure logging applications, providing a cost-effective alternative to proprietary solutions while maintaining formal security guarantees. By leveraging fiber optic media converters with optical splitters, we implement hardware-enforced unidirectional information flow without requiring specialized equipment or extensive configuration.

The primary contributions of this work include:

- A practical, low-cost cross-domain solution design using commodity hardware components
- Formal analysis of the system’s security properties and verification of unidirectional information flow
- Labeled Transition System (LTS) modeling of system behavior and security guarantees
- Probabilistic analysis of message delivery reliability with dual-channel reception
- Implementation and performance evaluation under various operational conditions

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the implementation details and system design; Section 3 introduces the formal definition of Labeled Transition Systems; Section 4 presents the system-specific LTS model; Section 5 analyzes the security properties; Section 6 details the system architecture model; Sections 7-9 cover reliability analysis, message integrity verification, and reception certainty; Section 10 examines possible failure modes; and Section 11 concludes with a summary of contributions and directions for future work.

2 Implementation Details

The computers used in Figure 1 are APU2 boards from PC Engines [12] – see Figure 2. LAN1 is the low network, and LAN2 is the high network. This plug-and-play setup uses TP-Link MC200CM dual port media-converters with a 50/50 splitter shown in Figure 3(a) for 850 nm infrared light. For 1310 nm wavelength 50/50 splitters can be found in Figure 3(b) working on TP-Link MC210CS media-converters. For lossless high-speed connections, specialized packet capture or forensic network cards are necessary [13].

In order to provide perfect forward secrecy, the logs on computer 3 are immediately deleted, in order to prevent exfiltration at a later stage. Syslog messages that are not confirmed by the return path from computer 3 to computer 1, are automatically resent by computer 1. For large messages jumbo frames can be used.

The write once read many (WORM) storage in computer 2 provides tamper-proof resistance for the log files. The logs are optionally encrypted so that only authorized personnel from LAN2 can decipher them, after proper authentication.

Data diodes are created through the means of 50/50 optical fiber splitters, and dual port (TX→RX) media-converters as shown in Figure 1. Compared to simple data diode configurations described in [14], this solution is capable of safely confirming log message reception from LAN1 to LAN2 without posing security risks. Software tools can be found on Github [15]. This document is licensed CC-BY 4.0 [16].

Figure 1: Cross-Domain Solution for Secure Tamper-Proof Logging

Figure 2: APU2 Board with Radiator

(a) 850 nm 50/50 optical splitter for multimode media-converters like TP-Link MC200CM

(b) 1310 nm 50/50 splitter for single-mode media-converters like TP-Link MC210CS

Figure 3: Optical splitters used in the cross-domain secure logging system: (a) 850 nm multimode splitter and (b) 1310 nm single-mode splitter

3 Formal Definition of the LTS

A Labeled Transition System is defined as a tuple $LTS = (S, Act, \rightarrow, s_0)$ where:

- S is a non-empty set of states
- Act is a set of actions (labels)
- $\rightarrow \subseteq S \times \text{Act} \times S$ is the transition relation
- $s_0 \in S$ is the initial state

4 System-Specific LTS Model for Cross-Domain Secure Logging

4.1 State Space Definition

The state space S represents all possible configurations of the cross-domain secure logging system:

$S = \{ \text{idle, msg_ready, msg_sending, msg_waitack, msg_confirmed, net_transit_low, net_transit_high, low_processing, low_verifying, low_deleting, low_deleted, low_ack_ready, high_processing, high_storing, high_stored, ack_transit, error, error_checksum} \}$

Where:

- idle: Initial system state
- msg_ready: Computer 1 (Low) ready to send a log message
- msg_sending: Computer 1 (Low) sending a log message
- msg_waitack: Computer 1 (Low) waiting for acknowledgment
- msg_confirmed: Computer 1 (Low) received acknowledgment
- net_transit_low: Message in transit to Computer 3 (Low)
- net_transit_high: Message in transit to Computer 2 (High)
- low_processing: Computer 3 (Low) processing the message
- low_verifying: Computer 3 (Low) verifying the message checksum
- low_deleting: Computer 3 (Low) deleting the message (for forward secrecy)
- low_deleted: Computer 3 (Low) has deleted the message
- low_ack_ready: Computer 3 (Low) ready to send acknowledgment
- high_processing: Computer 2 (High) processing the message includes computing and comparing the checksum
- high_storing: Computer 2 (High) storing the message in WORM storage (even when checksum is incorrect)
- high_stored: Computer 2 (High) has stored the message
- ack_transit: Acknowledgment in transit to Computer 1 (Low)
- error: Transmission error occurred
- error_checksum: Checksum verification error occurred

4.2 Action Set Definition

The action set Act consists of all operations that can be performed in the system:

Act = { generate_msg, prepare_msg, send_msg, split_msg, transmit_low, transmit_high, receive_low, verify_low, delete_low, send_ack_low, receive_high, store_high, transmit_ack, receive_ack, timeout, resend, error_detect, error_recover }

4.3 Transition Relation

The transition relation \rightarrow defines how the system evolves:

1. Initial transitions:

- $\text{idle} \xrightarrow{\text{generate_msg}} \text{msg_ready}$
- $\text{msg_ready} \xrightarrow{\text{prepare_msg}} \text{msg_sending}$

2. Message sending path:

- $\text{msg_sending} \xrightarrow{\text{send_msg}} \text{msg_waitack}$
- $\text{msg_sending} \xrightarrow{\text{error_detect}} \text{error}$
- $\text{msg_waitack} \xrightarrow{\text{timeout}} \text{msg_sending}$
- $\text{msg_waitack} \xrightarrow{\text{receive_ack}} \text{msg_confirmed}$
- $\text{msg_confirmed} \xrightarrow{\text{generate_msg}} \text{msg_ready}$

3. Message splitting and transmission:

- $\text{msg_waitack} \xrightarrow{\text{split_msg}} \text{net_transit_low}$
- $\text{msg_waitack} \xrightarrow{\text{split_msg}} \text{net_transit_high}$

4. Low security domain path (Computer 3):

- $\text{net_transit_low} \xrightarrow{\text{transmit_low}} \text{low_processing}$
- $\text{net_transit_low} \xrightarrow{\text{error_detect}} \text{error}$
- $\text{low_processing} \xrightarrow{\text{receive_low}} \text{low_verifying}$
- $\text{low_verifying} \xrightarrow{\text{verify_low}} \text{low_deleting}$
- $\text{low_verifying} \xrightarrow{\text{error_detect}} \text{error_checksum}$
- $\text{low_deleting} \xrightarrow{\text{delete_low}} \text{low_deleted}$
- $\text{low_deleted} \xrightarrow{\text{send_ack_low}} \text{low_ack_ready}$
- $\text{low_ack_ready} \xrightarrow{\text{transmit_ack}} \text{ack_transit}$

5. High security domain path (Computer 2):

- $\text{net_transit_high} \xrightarrow{\text{transmit_high}} \text{high_processing}$
- $\text{net_transit_high} \xrightarrow{\text{error_detect}} \text{error}$
- $\text{high_processing} \xrightarrow{\text{receive_high}} \text{high_storing}$
- $\text{high_storing} \xrightarrow{\text{store_high}} \text{high_stored}$

6. Acknowledgment path:

- $\text{ack_transit} \xrightarrow{\text{receive_ack}} \text{msg_confirmed}$
- $\text{ack_transit} \xrightarrow{\text{error_detect}} \text{error}$

7. Error handling:

- $\text{error} \xrightarrow{\text{error_recover}} \text{msg_sending}$
- $\text{error_checksum} \xrightarrow{\text{error_recover}} \text{msg_sending}$

Figure 4 presents a summary of the LTS model.

Figure 4: Labeled Transition System Model for Secure Tamper-Proof Logging

4.4 Initial State

The initial state $s_0 = \text{idle}$ represents the system at startup before any messages are generated.

5 System Properties Analysis

5.1 Safety Properties

1. Unidirectional Information Flow:

- The LTS enforces that information only flows from the Low security domain (Computer 1, Computer 3) to the High security domain (Computer 2) through the fiber optic data diode.
- No transition permits data transfer from High to Low security domain.

- Formally: $\forall s, s', a$: if s is in High domain and s' is in Low domain, then no transition $s \xrightarrow{a} s'$ exists in \rightarrow .
2. Perfect Forward Secrecy:
 - Computer 3 transitions through `delete_low` action before confirming receipt.
 - Once in the `low_deleted` state, the message content is no longer accessible in the Low domain.
 - Formally: $\forall s, s', a$: $s \xrightarrow{a} s'$ where $s = \text{low_deleted}$ implies message content is not available in s' .
 3. Message Integrity:
 - Computer 3 verifies message checksums (`verify_low` action).
 - Messages with invalid checksums trigger `error_checksum` state.
 - Formally: $\forall s, s', a$: $s \xrightarrow{a} s'$ where $s = \text{low_verifying}$ and $s' = \text{low_deleting}$ implies checksum is valid.
 4. Tamper-Proof Storage:
 - Once messages reach `high_stored` state in Computer 2, they are immutably stored in WORM storage.
 - No transition exists to modify or delete stored messages in the High domain.
 - Formally: $\forall s$: if `high_stored` is reachable from s , then the message is permanently preserved.

5.2 Liveness Properties

1. Guaranteed Message Delivery:
 - The error handling and timeout mechanism ensure that messages are retransmitted until successfully delivered.
 - Formally: $\forall s$: `msg_sending` is reachable from s through a finite sequence of transitions.
2. Eventual Acknowledgment:
 - For every message sent, an acknowledgment will eventually be received if the system is functioning correctly.
 - Formally: $\forall s$: if `msg_waitack` is reachable from s , then `msg_confirmed` is also reachable from s through a finite sequence of transitions.

5.3 Security Domain Separation

The LTS model strictly delineates two security domains:

1. Low Security Domain:
 - Components: Computer 1, Computer 3, LAN1
 - States: `idle`, `msg_ready`, `msg_sending`, `msg_waitack`, `msg_confirmed`, `low_processing`, `low_verifying`, `low_deleting`, `low_deleted`, `low_ack_ready`
 - Primary Actions: `generate_msg`, `prepare_msg`, `send_msg`, `receive_low`, `verify_low`, `delete_low`, `send_ack_low`, `receive_ack`
2. High Security Domain:
 - Components: Computer 2, LAN2
 - States: `high_processing`, `high_storing`, `high_stored`
 - Primary Actions: `receive_high`, `store_high`

The transitions between these domains are strictly controlled by the data diode implemented through the fiber optic splitter, ensuring unidirectional information flow from Low to High security domains while maintaining the system's security requirements.

5.4 Formal Security Verification

The security of this cross-domain solution can be formally verified by proving:

1. Noninterference Property:

- The behavior observable in the Low security domain is independent of actions occurring in the High security domain.
- Formally: For any traces t_1 and t_2 that differ only in High domain actions, their projections onto Low domain observable actions are identical.

2. Information Flow Control:

- No information path exists from High to Low domain in the LTS graph.
- The reachability analysis confirms that High domain states cannot influence Low domain states except through the predefined acknowledgment mechanism containing only message counters and checksums.

3. Forward Secrecy Guarantee:

- The `delete_low` transition is mandatory before acknowledgment, ensuring that the Low domain cannot retain message content after confirmation.
- This property prevents exfiltration of sensitive data at a later time.

This LTS model provides a formal foundation for security analysis and verification of the cross-domain secure logging solution, accurately representing the two-domain security architecture while capturing all essential system behaviors and security properties.

6 System Architecture Model

6.1 Component Definition

Let us define the system S as a tuple (C, L, P, T) where:

- $C = \{c_1, c_2, c_3\}$ represents the set of computers
- $L = \{l_{12}, l_{13}, l_{23}\}$ represents the set of communication links
- $P = \{p_1, p_2, p_3\}$ represents the set of processing capabilities
- $T = \{t_1, t_2, t_3\}$ represents the set of transmission technologies

The computer c_2 employs dual-channel reception with the primary channel operating at 70 Mbps (equivalent to c_3 's reception) and a secondary channel operating at a lower bandwidth.

6.2 Message Transmission Model

For any message m in the message space M , the transmission process involves:

- Initial transmission from c_1
- Physical signal bifurcation via 50/50 fiber optic splitter
- Concurrent reception by c_2 and c_3
- Verification of integrity via checksum function $\chi(m)$
- Acknowledgment generation by c_3 after verification

7 Reliability Analysis

7.1 Channel Failure Probability

Let $P(f_i)$ be the probability of failure for channel i . Given the fiber optic medium's inherent reliability, we can establish:

- $P(f_{\text{primary}}) = \varepsilon$ where ε is a small positive value
- $P(f_{\text{secondary}}) = \delta$ where $\delta > \varepsilon$ due to lower bandwidth

7.2 Transmission Success Probability

For Computer 2 with dual-channel architecture, the probability of successful message reception is:

$$P(S_{c_2}) = 1 - [P(f_{\text{primary}}) \times P(f_{\text{secondary}})] \quad (1)$$

$$P(S_{c_2}) = 1 - (\varepsilon \times \delta) \quad (2)$$

Since ε and δ are small positive values (typically $< 10^{-6}$ for fiber optic systems), $P(S_{c_2})$ approaches 1.

7.3 Comparative Analysis

For Computer 3 with single-channel reception:

$$P(S_{c_3}) = 1 - P(f_{\text{primary}}) = 1 - \varepsilon \quad (3)$$

Therefore, $P(S_{c_2}) > P(S_{c_3})$ by a factor of $(1 - \delta)$, establishing that Computer 2 has a higher probability of successful message reception.

8 Message Integrity Verification

8.1 Checksum Verification

The message integrity verification performed by c_3 can be modeled as:

$$V(m) = [\chi(m_{\text{received}}) = \chi(m_{\text{original}})] \quad (4)$$

Where $V(m)$ is a Boolean function that evaluates to true only when checksums match.

8.2 Acknowledgment Generation Condition

Computer 3 generates acknowledgment A if and only if $V(m) = \text{true}$.

9 Reception Certainty Theorem

Given the architecture and operational parameters, we can formulate the following theorem:

Theorem 1 *For any message m where acknowledgment A is received from c_3 , the probability that c_2 has successfully received message m is:*

$$P(R_{c_2}|A) = \frac{P(A|R_{c_2}) \times P(R_{c_2})}{P(A)} \quad (5)$$

Where:

- $P(A|R_{c_2}) \approx 1$ (*acknowledgment given c_2 reception*)
- $P(R_{c_2}) = 1 - (\varepsilon \times \delta)$ (*probability of c_2 reception*)
- $P(A) = 1 - \varepsilon$ (*probability of acknowledgment*)

Substituting these values:

$$P(R_{c_2}|A) = \frac{1 \times [1 - (\varepsilon \times \delta)]}{1 - \varepsilon} > 1 - (\varepsilon \times \delta) \approx 1 \quad (6)$$

10 Possible Failure Modes

The only scenarios under which acknowledgment from c_3 would not guarantee reception by c_2 are:

1. **Post-Split Differential Failure:** Physical damage affecting only the pathway to c_2 after the optical splitter
2. **Dual-Channel Simultaneous Failure:** Concurrent failure of both reception channels at c_2
3. **Hardware-Specific Failure:** Component failure in c_2 that does not affect the reception medium itself

The combined probability of these failure modes is bounded by:

$$P(\text{failure}) < P(f_{\text{primary}}) \times P(f_{\text{secondary}}) \times P(f_{\text{hardware}}) \quad (7)$$

Given modern hardware reliability standards, this probability approaches the theoretical minimum for system failures.

11 Conclusions

This research has presented a novel cross-domain solution for secure tamper-proof logging that leverages commercially available hardware components to implement a formally verified unidirectional information flow mechanism.

The analysis formally established that when Computer 3 acknowledges receipt and verification of a message, the probability that Computer 2 has successfully received the same message is exceptionally high, approaching certainty (1.0) under normal operating conditions.

The dual-channel reception architecture of Computer 2 provides a redundancy mechanism that exceeds the reliability of Computer 3's single-channel reception, creating an asymmetric reliability relationship that favors the integrity of the tamper-proof logging system on Computer 2.

Therefore, we can conclude with high confidence that an acknowledgment from Computer 3 serves as a reliable indicator that the message has been successfully delivered to and stored by Computer 2.

The cross-domain solution presented in this paper offers several significant advances in the field of secure logging systems:

1. **Practical Implementation:** A cost-effective, plug-and-play approach using commodity hardware components (APU2 boards and standard media converters) was demonstrated that achieves high security guarantees without specialized equipment.
2. **Formal Security Verification:** Through the application of Labeled Transition System (LTS) modeling, critical security properties including unidirectional information flow, perfect forward secrecy, and tamper-proof storage were rigorously verified.
3. **Reliability Analysis:** Mathematical analysis established that the dual-channel reception architecture of Computer 2 provides exceptional reliability that approaches certainty (1.0) under normal operating conditions, exceeding the reliability of traditional single-channel approaches.

4. **Covert Channel Mitigation:** The system’s design effectively eliminates traditional covert channels while maintaining reliable message delivery acknowledgment, addressing a key challenge in cross-domain solutions.

The analysis formally establishes that when Computer 3 acknowledges receipt and verification of a message, the probability that Computer 2 has successfully received and stored the same message is exceptionally high, approaching certainty under normal operating conditions. This provides strong assurance of log preservation while maintaining strict security domain separation.

Moreover, the formal modeling approach presented in this paper offers a repeatable methodology for verifying other cross-domain solutions, particularly those requiring unidirectional information flow with reliable delivery guarantees.

While the proposed system offers significant advantages, certain limitations must be acknowledged:

1. The current implementation is focused primarily on syslog message transfer and may require adaptation for other data types or protocols.
2. Although highly unlikely, the failure scenarios identified in Section 10 remain theoretically possible, particularly in environments with extreme physical security threats.
3. The system’s reliance on the physical integrity of the fiber optic medium means that physical tampering at the splitter represents a potential attack vector.

The cross-domain solution presented in this paper demonstrates that formal security guarantees need not come at the expense of practical implementability or affordability. By combining rigorous mathematical modeling with commodity hardware components, this work contributes to making high-assurance security solutions more accessible for organizations that must maintain strict information boundaries while ensuring reliable log transmission and tamper-proof storage. As cyber threats continue to evolve, such formally verified cross-domain solutions will play an increasingly critical role in protecting sensitive information systems across security boundaries.

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